

QUIZ**LAST NAME: TANDAMAT****FIRST NAME: NELES****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Writing tools and Linguistic Standard I used in this Response Paper (RP):**

I applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

Turabian (in-text/parenthetical) referencing style

Application of Zotero to insert references

Application of Grammarly Premium provided by Euclid University for Grammar check

I applied MSWord 2010 on Windows 11 as the standard software.

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Plagiarism is:

- When the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- When the writer uses his own information and gives credit to other sources of information.
- When the writer uses both footnote referencing style and author-date style citations in giving credit to the source of information.
- When someone write a paper for you without you giving credit to the author of your paper.

¹Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021, 5).

2. **What are some rules of thumb for writing papers?**

- Rules of thumb for writing papers are; (1) state the central thesis at the beginning, (2) stay focused, (3) do not start with or include sweeping statements, (4) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, (5) support assertions, (6) read your paper out loud, and (7) do not plagiarize.
- Rules of thumb for writing papers are; (1) state the central thesis at the beginning, (2) stay focused, (3) do not start with or include sweeping statements, (4) write clearly, (5) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, (6) support assertions, and (7) do not plagiarize.
- Rules of thumb for writing papers are; (1) state the central thesis at the beginning, (2) stay focused, (3) do not start with or include sweeping statements, (4) write clearly, (5) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, (6) support assertions, (7) take the views you are discussing seriously, (8) read your paper out loud, (9) use the first person singular, and (10) do not plagiarize.²**
- Rules of thumb for writing papers are; (1) state the central thesis at the beginning, (2) stay focused, (3) do not start with or include sweeping statements, (4) write clearly, (5) do not make the writing boring and clumsy, (6) support assertions, (7) allow a friend to read for you, (8) correct spelling mistakes, (9) insert references, and (10) do not plagiarize.

3. **Which of the reminders is not one of the eleven (11) essential reminders in a literature review?**

- Make the subject and verb agree with each other, not with a word that comes between them.
- Apply capital letters sparingly.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 14-16.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 17-23.

- Use parallel construction to make a strong point and create a smooth flow.
 - Omit unnecessary words.
4. **Publishing industries and educational institutions adopt institutional style guides for writing; state one of the primary reasons for adopting a specific style guide?**
- To avoid plagiarism.
 - To compete with other industries.
 - To ensure the public read and respond to the text in the same writing style.
 - To maintain consistency in the writing style.⁴**
5. **Research is a _____**
- Process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that a researcher, including the society, aspires to solve.⁵**
 - Simple formula that researchers begin by stating: I am working on X to find out Y so that others can better understand Z.
 - Question worth answering.
 - Question that you aspire to find an answer that you can support with good reason and apply reliable data to support them as evidence.
6. **Three categories of sources in research are:**
- _____

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-26.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne Booth C. et al., 9th ed. (Chicago, USA and London: Chicago University Press, 2018, 19).

- Secondary sources, Current sources, and tertiary sources
- Tertiary sources, recorded materials, and secondary sources.
- Internet sources, library sources, and recorded materials.
- Primary sources, secondary sources, and tertiary sources.**⁶

7. **Which statement about research and dissertation is true?**

- Taking charge of self and work at the beginning of the study is not essential to improving your research.
- There are three essential aspects that a researcher must identify at the beginning of a research project. They include; (1) identifying the potential audience of your study, (2) identifying the intellectual value and worth of your study, and (3) identifying personal and professional goals.
- Generalization and ambiguity in a research topic do not come from the problem statement therefore must be narrowed down to a specific study area.
- The literature review is essential for every dissertation paper because it fulfils the research tradition and places your contribution among the research publications.**⁷

8. **Which statement about the conclusion of a dissertation below is false?**

- Before defending your research, take time to revise, craft a title, and finalize the introduction.
- Proofreading can disorient your research topic.**⁸

⁶ Turabian , 35.

⁷ [Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Writing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* \(Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008\), 139-140.](#)

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 200.

- Structuring the conclusion and recommendations of findings in the research are shortened by Bloomberg and Volpe as follows; finding statement – interpretations – conclusions – recommendations.
- In general, a dissertation usually contains six chapters. The chapters come in the following order; introduction, literature review, methodology, analyzing and reporting findings, and conclusions and recommendations.

9. **For the speakers of both English and French, what effects can affect their communication when switching between the two languages?**

- Confusion effects.
- Pairing effects.
- Interference effects.**⁹
- Side effects.

10. **The two major legal documents that regulate all EU operations are:**

- Primary Legislation and Secondary Legislation.**¹⁰
- Regulations and Directives.
- Primary Legislation and Treaties.
- Secondary Legislation and Treaties.

⁹ European Commission, 22.

¹⁰ European Commission, 74-80.

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